

Electrochemical Reduction of Flunitrazepam and its Determination in Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms by Differential Pulse Polarography

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Manuscript received 22 August 1995, revised 28 February 1996, accepted 8 March 1996

A simple, rapid differential pulse polarographic method has been developed for the determination of flunitrazepam in pharmaceutical dosage forms using universal buffers of pH 2–6. The substance is extracted from the dosage forms with dimethylformamide, an appropriate buffer of selected pH is added to an aliquot and the solution then polarographed at dropping mercury electrode vs SCE. The electrochemical reduction behaviour of flunitrazepam has been studied by employing d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography using universal buffers of pH 2–12. The two-step reduction wave/peak observed is found to be irreversible and diffusion-controlled. Kinetic parameters are evaluated and reduction mechanism is proposed. The standard addition method provides results as satisfactory as those obtained with the use of a calibration graph.

Flunitrazepam [5-(2-fluorophenyl)-1,3-dihydro-1-methyl-7-nitro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepine] (FNZ) is a benzodiazepine compound mainly used as tranquiliser, hypnotics, sedative and antidepressant¹. Some reviews² have been published on the determination of 1,4-benzodiazepine and their metabolites in formulations and biological fluids using d.c. polarography.

The purpose of this work is to establish the experimental conditions that permit the study of the electrochemical reduction of the titled compound using the techniques such as d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography, and a method is suggested for its determination with enhanced selectivity.

Results and Discussion

Flunitrazepam exhibits a two-step reduction wave/peak in the pH range 2–12 and two well-separated waves/peaks of almost equal heights in the pH range 2–6. The first wave/

peak is attributed to the reduction of nitro group to hydroxylamine in a four-electron process which appears at the start of potential and the second wave/peak to the simultaneous reduction of the azomethine and hydroxylamine groups leading to the formation of amine involving two electrons each. However, in alkaline solutions (pH 8–12), FNZ shows a two-step reduction process. It is assumed that the identical four-electron reduction of nitro group is followed by a mechanism corresponding to the two-electron reduction of this leading to the saturation. It is also evident from the fact that in alkaline solution, second wave/peak is observed to have half the height of the first wave/peak as hydroxylamine does not get further reduced owing to non-availability of protons. Typical polarograms are shown in Figs. 1–4.

In cyclic voltammetry also, two cathodic peaks C_1 and C_2 are observed in alkaline media due to the reduction of the nitro group and the hydroxylamine groups respectively. But an anodic peak a_1 in the first reverse scan has been noticed at higher pH values (pH > 10). In the second scan, another small cathodic peak C_2 at more positive potentials than C_1 is noticed. The anodic peak a_1 may be due to the

Fig. 1. Typical d.c. polarogram of flunitrazepam at pH 2; conc. = 0.5 mM, drop time = 3 s.

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram of flunitrazepam at pH 6; conc. = 0.5 mM, scan rate = 40 mV s⁻¹.

Fig. 3. Typical a.c. polarogram of flunitrazepam at pH 4; conc. = 0.5 mM, drop time = 3 s: (a) a.c. peak and (b) base peak.

Fig. 4. Typical differential pulse polarogram of flunitrazepam at pH 13; conc. = 0.5 mM, drop time = 2 s.

oxidation of the hydroxylamine formed at C_1 to the nitroso derivative and the cathodic peak C_2 to the reduction of the nitroso derivative to the hydroxylamine again³. This redox couple is observed to be irreversible as evidenced from the separation of their peak potential values. Both the waves were found to be irreversible, diffusion-controlled and adsorption-free in the buffer systems studied as shown by the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ and i_p vs $V^{1/2}$ passing through the origin. The current function values $i_p/cV^{1/2}$ were found to be constant with respect to the scan rate (V), indicating the electrode process to be free from any kinetic complications. The irreversible nature of the two waves/peaks for FNZ are seen from the variation of reduction potential with the concentration of the depolariser, log-plot analysis, disobedience of Tome's criterion and nonlinearity in the i_m vs $(1-\sigma)/(1+\sigma)$ plots. From the slope of $E^{1/2}$ vs pH plot, the number of protons involved in the rate-determining step of the nitro group reduction was found to be one.

The number of electrons involved in the overall reduction of FNZ, as determined by millicoulometry, was found

to be four for both steps in pH 2. But in alkaline media (pH > 10), the number of electrons for the first wave was found to be four and for the second wave two only. The gradual decrease and final disappearance of the uv-absorption peak of the catholyte solution in the range of 310–380 nm indicate that the nitro group is one of the reduction sites of the electrochemical reduction of FNZ. The catholyte solution is subjected to the controlled potential electrolysis at pH 2.0 at -0.15 V vs SCE and the product is identified as the corresponding amine (ν_{\max} , nujol: 3 450, 1 600 cm^{-1}). Typical kinetic parameters for the electrode process evaluated from different techniques are reported in Table 1. The variation of diffusion current and peak current with the pH of the supporting electrolyte influences the diffusion coefficient values also to vary in the same manner.

The forward rate constant values for the reduction of nitro group when compared to that of azomethine group are found to be high, since the reduction of nitro group is facile as evidenced from the less negative reduction potential. The forward rate constant values obtained for the reduction of nitro as well as azomethine groups are found to decrease with increase in pH of the solution.

On the basis of the results obtained from different techniques, a reduction mechanism as shown in Scheme 1 can be proposed for FNZ in different pH zones.

Analysis: Both the polarographic peaks obtained in the pH ranges are well resolved and may be utilised for the analysis of pharmaceutical preparations. However, first peak being highly reproducible was chosen for the analysis of the powder dosage forms of FNZ. The optimum pH range for obtaining well resolved peaks was found to be $4 \leq \text{pH} \leq 6$. The optimum conditions for the determination of FNZ at pH 4 was found to have a drop time of 2 s and pulse amplitude of 60 mV. The relative standard deviation and

TABLE 1—TYPICAL ELECTRODE DATA OF FLUNITRAZEPAM

Supporting electrolyte of pH	D.C. polarography drop time : 3 s			Cyclic voltammetry scan rate : 60 mV/s			A.C. polarography drop time : 2 s			Differential pulse polarography drop time : 2 s			
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$D > 10^5$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	K_{fh}^* cm s^{-1}	$-E_p$ V	$D > 10^5$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	K_{fh}^* cm s^{-1}	$-E_s$ V	$D > 10^5$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	K_s^* cm s^{-1}	$-E_m$ V	$D \times 10^5$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	K_{fh}^* cm s^{-1}	
2	(a)	0.08	2.68	1.22×10^{-4}	0.09	2.77	1.72×10^{-4}	0.08	2.65	1.87×10^{-2}	0.07	2.66	1.79×10^{-4}
	(b)	0.69	2.59	4.36×10^{-9}	0.70	2.60	8.42×10^{-9}	0.69	2.60	8.31×10^{-5}	0.69	2.51	4.87×10^{-9}
4	(a)	0.22	2.60	3.44×10^{-5}	0.25	2.62	3.98×10^{-5}	0.24	2.49	2.03×10^{-3}	0.23	2.52	1.43×10^{-5}
	(b)	0.89	2.48	5.51×10^{-10}	0.92	2.53	5.74×10^{-11}	0.89	2.29	4.43×10^{-7}	0.89	2.41	2.54×10^{-9}
6	(a)	0.43	2.16	7.37×10^{-6}	0.46	2.23	2.18×10^{-6}	0.49	2.13	7.43×10^{-4}	0.45	2.20	1.87×10^{-6}
	(b)	1.01	2.04	1.34×10^{-11}	1.04	2.11	1.82×10^{-12}	1.03	1.98	8.48×10^{-8}	1.03	2.11	5.44×10^{-10}
8	(a)	0.52	2.11	2.94×10^{-8}	0.51	2.10	6.31×10^{-7}	0.50	1.95	2.84×10^{-5}	0.54	2.01	5.89×10^{-8}
	(b)	1.13	1.43	1.88×10^{-13}	1.13	1.34	2.94×10^{-13}	1.11	1.35	5.57×10^{-10}	1.13	1.43	6.97×10^{-12}
10	(a)	0.61	1.85	4.01×10^{-9}	0.63	1.96	1.61×10^{-9}	0.61	1.81	2.03×10^{-6}	0.61	1.85	6.83×10^{-9}
	(b)	1.15	1.07	8.79×10^{-15}	1.20	1.10	9.30×10^{-15}	1.17	1.02	3.14×10^{-12}	1.20	1.03	2.35×10^{-14}
12	(a)	0.69	1.82	4.54×10^{-10}	0.70	1.89	5.39×10^{-10}	0.68	1.80	8.71×10^{-7}	0.70	1.69	6.01×10^{-10}
	(b)	1.23	1.00	6.10×10^{-18}	1.27	1.10	1.23×10^{-18}	1.23	0.97	5.59×10^{-13}	1.27	0.93	5.11×10^{-17}

correlation coefficient were 1.84% and 0.98% respectively, for 10 replicants.

The described analytical procedure was utilised for the determination of FNZ in pharmaceutical formulations (Table 2). The recoveries, which are in the range 98.0–98.6%, indicate the high accuracy and reproducibility of the method. Pharmaceutical excipients commonly employed with formulations such as those examined here did not interfere with the assay. The method is simple, sensitive and rapid.

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF FLUNITRAZEPAM DOSAGE FORM BY DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY

pH = 4, pulse amplitude = 60 mV, drop time = 2 s

Sample	Labelled amount mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Standard deviation %
Rohypnol	2.5	2.45	98.0	3.7
Rohypnol	5.0	4.93	98.6	1.6

Experimental

The theoretical details and experimental procedure have been discussed elsewhere⁴.

FNZ (Sigma) was used as such. The stock solution (10^{-3} M) of FNZ was prepared in dimethyl-formamide. All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The supporting electrolytes (pH 2–12) were prepared using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.1 M trisodium orthophosphate⁵. A 0.2% aqueous solution of Triton X-100 was used⁶ to eliminate the polarographic maxima encountered. In order to establish the reliability and suitability of the proposed method, known amounts of the pure drug were added to various pre-analysed formulations of FNZ and mixtures were analysed by the proposed method.

Differential pulse polarographic technique was used for the quantitative determination of FNZ using calibration and standard addition methods. Linear calibration range lies between 1.5×10^{-5} and 2.5×10^{-7} M at pH 4.

Procedure : Flunitrazepam was available in tablet dosage forms. A mixture of the finely ground sample (containing 25–30 mg of FNZ, corresponding to a stock solution of concentration 1×10^{-5} M) was mixed with DMF and shaken for 20 min, diluted to 100 ml with DMF and filtered. An aliquot (1 ml) of the clear filtrate and the appropriate buffer (9 ml) of selected pH were placed in the cell and the polarograms recorded after deaeration for 15 min with N_2 gas. After taking the polarogram, standard solution of FNZ (0.1 ml) was added to it, deaerated for 2 min and polarogram again recorded under identical condition. The wave heights (H) and h were measured and the mass of FNZ per formulation was calculated using the equation,

$$\text{Mass} = \frac{a h b \times 100}{(1.10 H - h)W}$$

Where, a (mg) is the mass of FNZ reference standard in 100 ml of standard solution, b (g) the average mass of a tablet or capsule, W (mg) the mass of sample taken for the polarographic determination, h the wave height of FNZ before standard additions, H the wave height of FNZ after standard additions and 1.10 is the dilution factor.

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